

A Content Analysis of Tourists' Return Intention in Magic Kingdom Theme Park - Walt Disney World

¹Carolene R. Demonteverde, ²Earnsdale D. Navarro, ³Karl Marco H. Rebote, ⁴Deogracias E. Esplanada

^{1,2,3} Proponents, ⁴Research Adviser
De La Salle University – Dasmariñas
College of Tourism and Hospitality Management
Dasmariñas, Cavite, Philippines

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8038074>

Published Date: 14-June-2023

Abstract: Theme parks have grown in popularity around the world, not only because they are a popular source of major amusement, but also because they are a stress-relieving destination for both children and adults. At Walt Disney World, there are four different and unique destinations: EPCOT, Animal Kingdom, Hollywood Studios, and the Magic Kingdom, which is the most popular of the three. This qualitative study aims to acquire information from secondary data gathered from various YouTube vlogs in order to assist researchers in determining the elements that influence tourists' desire to return to Walt Disney World's Magic Kingdom Theme Park. Simultaneously, establish what strategies might be offered and developed to aid tourists' desire to return to the stated park, and other theme parks. Through content analysis, a qualitative research approach was employed to examine tourists' experiences, perceptions, and statements. In addition, data extraction employed a purposive sample strategy, with the YouTube videos (vlogs) from second-time or more visits to Walt Disney World's Magic Kingdom theme park. The study concludes that the image of the destination, level of happiness that tourists have with the site, infrastructure, natural and cultural surroundings, level of safety and security, and price, are all key elements that can greatly impact visitors' intents to return to a theme park. Several recommendations are then made for other theme and amusement parks to improve tourists' intention to return.

Keywords: Content Analysis, Purposive Sampling, Return Intention, Theme Park, Destination Image, Tourist Satisfaction, Infrastructure, Natural and Cultural, Safety and Security, Price.

I. INTRODUCTION

Tourism has been an essential element of the Florida economic system since the 1800s. Florida's economy is extremely diverse, with tourism and agriculture among its top industries. In 2019, the leisure and hotel sector contributed 6% to GDP growth. According to Visit Florida, international tourists and visitors from other states generated \$96.5 billion to Florida's economy, which is more than the other thirteen states combined (McLeod, 2021). The tourist industry in Florida attracted 122 million visitors in 2021, a 54 percent increase in 2020.

Orlando was among three Florida major cities to top Forbes' list of the Top 25 U.S travel destinations in 2020. Orlando reported a record-breaking 75 million yearly tourists in 2018, setting a turning point in the history for the United States tourism industry. The 4.2 percent increase over the following year strengthens Orlando's standing as America's most traveled destination. In 2019, 50.1 million tourists visited Orlando, representing a 6.7 percent increase from 2018. Furthermore, the city also receives the most visitors to Florida each year due to its various accommodations and theme parks.

During 1971, Walt Disney World’s Magic Kingdom transformed about 107 acres of Orlando into what is now known to be “the most magical place on earth”. The Walt Disney World Resort is a theme park renowned for its many attractions and experiences. It is the largest Disney Park in the world and contains more than 50 rides, shows and attractions. The Magic Kingdom is separated into six distinct regions (lands), placed in a spoke-like pattern, all meeting at the top of Main Street, U.S.A. right in front of Cinderella Castle. The six lands consist of Main Street, U.S.A., Tomorrowland, Fantasyland, Frontierland, Liberty Square, and Adventureland. Each land is tailored to its respective title and sustaining that theme is important to the park's management.

The theme park industry has emerged and evolved into a competitive and rapidly changing industry in recent years, involving its potential to simultaneously respond with customers’ needs and wants throughout the twenty-first century due to unprecedented challenges. The result of these challenges has reshaped the tourism market that brings a new generation of tourists with a demand for changes for specific reasons (diversity of destinations for new experiences, safety, etc.). With the increasing pressure for customers’ demands, the competition among destinations is growing as well. Hence, the importance of determining and understanding the factors that can affect tourists’ return intention is essential to assist small and big theme parks like Orlando’s Magic Kingdom.

The return intention in the tourism sector can be defined as the behavior of the tourist that involves their intent to revisit a certain destination or attraction (Khuong & Nguyen, 2017). Zhang, Wu, and Buhalis (2017) highlighted the importance of tourists' experiences in affecting their decision to return. As stated by Mai et al., (2019), tourist contentment and intent to return are regarded as critical factors in a destination's success.

Despite the advances in understanding the different factors that affect tourists' return intention, there are a limited number of studies that cover the return intention of tourists to theme parks. Hence, understanding the behavior of the tourists specifically when visiting a theme park is needed since there are many park attractions that possess the same resources and offer the same kind of service; the likelihood of tourists’ intention to return is unlikely even if their needs and expectations are met as they search for new experiences.

In a competitive industry, continuous improvement is essential. Theme parks can implement the systems or approaches used by the Magic Kingdom Theme Park. Hence, the general objective of this study is to determine the factors influencing visitors' intentions to return to Magic Kingdom Theme Park - Walt Disney World in the context of YouTube videos, as well as strategies that can be recommended and developed for other theme parks. The study will mainly benefit the Magic Kingdom Theme Park management, other theme parks, and future researchers. Additionally, to date, there are few international and domestic studies that tackle the return intention of tourists specifically on theme parks. The study aims to fill the gap with regard to the lack of research concentrating on the analysis of return intention relating to theme park tourism.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW AND THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Fig. 1 - Destination image, tourists' destination satisfaction, infrastructure, price, natural and cultural environment, and safety and security are the factors that have the greatest effect on tourists' return intention (Ngoc Khuong, Mai & Trinh, Nguyen, 2015). These factors will be used in proposing strategies to develop tourists’ return intention in Magic Kingdom - Walt Disney.

Figure 1: shows the researcher’s adapted conceptual framework based on the tourist return intention of Ngoc Khuong et al. (2015).

The concept of return intention comes from the philosophy of planned behavior. It is described as future decisions and actions that are intended or expected (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975). The theory of reasoned action and planned behavior is developed by Fishbein & Ajzen (1975). These cognitive theories are considered as an important conceptual framework for understanding and predicting human behavior. The reasoned action theory is a key in determining the person's behavior based on intentions, psychological (attitude), and subjective norms. The theory of planned behavior is developed through the reasoned action theory. It emphasizes that perceived behavioral control and behavioral intention predicts the behavior of a person. The return intention in the tourism sector can be defined as the behavior of the tourist that involves their intent to revisit a certain destination or attraction (Khuong & Nguyen, 2017). Zhang, Wu, and Buhalis (2017) highlighted the importance of tourists' experiences in affecting their decision to return. As stated by Mai et al., (2019), tourist contentment and intent to return are regarded as critical factors in a destination's success.

The researchers adapted the study based on the tourist return intention of Ngoc Khuong et al. (2015). There are six elements that influence tourist return intention, according to Ngoc Khuong et al. (2015), namely, (1) destination image, destination tourist satisfaction, infrastructural facilities, price, natural and cultural environment, and safety and security.

Destination Image

In terms of tourists' return intention, destination image does have a significant influence (Zhang, et al., 2017). The concept of destination image was defined by Jebbouri, et al. (2022) as the collection of beliefs, ideas, and impressions that a tourist has to a destination or attraction.

Tourists' Destination Satisfaction

Satisfaction is a relationship's result between tourists' expectations about the destination based on their previous destination's images and experiences' evaluation at the destination, or "function of pre-travel expectations and travel experiences" or comparison's results between tourists' experiences at the destination and the expectations about the destination. Tourists' satisfaction is significant to achieve high visitors' intention in revisiting the same destination. Tourists' satisfaction is the comparison of the relationship between the pre-travel expectations or tourists' expectations based on their destination image and travel experiences from other places. Milman and Tasci (2017) also investigated if satisfaction and loyalty were influenced by past visits, the number of past visits, and staying overnight at the theme park's destination. The results pointed out the influence of overnight stays on the level of satisfaction, and the influence of the number of past visits on the likelihood to revisit theme parks.

Infrastructure

According to Jovanovi et al. (2016), tourism infrastructure is referred to as a physical feature that is designed and built to accommodate tourists. Infrastructure, which comprises air, land, sea, and leisure facilities such as accommodations and car rentals, is key to traveling and tourism efficiency, notably in revisiting a destination. These infrastructures comprise supporting amenities, equipment, and manpower which are essential to the operation of any tourism destination.

Price

The price that customers pay in exchange for products, services' benefits, service level, and quality may also be influenced by the destination's association with lavish imagery and sophistication, for which customers are willing to pay a higher price. In the study conducted by Khuong (2015), it was also found that price had a substantial beneficial effect on tourists' desire to return.

Natural and Cultural Environment

Tourism creates interest toward a specific place rich in heritage, elegance, and greatness. According to Tifferet and Vilnai-Yavetz (2017), nature elements in a commercial environment can affect emotional responses of satisfaction or, to a small extent, customer behavior. Cultural and tourism have a mutual association which can improve the viability and competitiveness of places, districts, and states. Tourists are anticipated to achieve a better understanding of the heritage of all such tourist destinations from experiences with local customs and locals (H. Chen & Rahman, 2018). Zeng (2017) stated that a destination's culture becomes more intriguing and appealing to long-distance tourists.

Safety and Security

While safety and security is primarily concerned with protecting individuals from hazards and guaranteeing environmental security, there is still a distinction between the two. Security refers to the protection against criminal actions, whereas safety refers to the protection of human life and health. Because the safety and security situation in Vung Tau city is not very good, it has a negative impact on the tourists' desire to return.

According to the study of Ryani and Soesanto (2021), satisfaction is what service providers expect which greatly influences customer loyalty attitudes, many previous studies have stated that satisfaction is the key or strongest factor in purchasing or repeat visits. It was also mentioned that Disneyland, Universal Studios, Universal's Island of Adventure Orlando, and so on are the best playgrounds that have many visitors. The quantitative study that they have conducted is about the factors that can affect revisit intention through customer satisfaction in a theme park. In this study the researchers utilized Nonprobability Sampling technique with accidental sampling and Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) to test various hypotheses. The findings indicated that Physical attributes have a positive effect on customer satisfaction and intention to return; Interaction with customers has a positive effect on customer satisfaction and interest in returning to visit; Interaction with employees has a positive effect on customer satisfaction and interest in returning to visit; customer satisfaction has a positive effect on interest in returning to visit.

Wu, Li, and Li (2018) determined the relationships between experiential quality, experiential value, experiential satisfaction, theme park image, and revisit intention perceived by visitors in three different theme parks, namely, Universal Studios, Disney World, and SeaWorld. With the use of RapidMiner Studio, the researchers were able to collect sentiment scores for each theme park. Factor analysis, to identify the underlying structure of visitor reviews, and lastly, Anova and comparison analysis to compare the differences of satisfaction ratings and sentiments of visitors among the three theme parks. Overall, the results of the study suggests that tangible and physical environment in a theme park is the most important determinant of experiential quality perceived by theme park visitors.

The theme park's make-up service (Halloween, Zombie, Fairy, Cartoon Character, and so on) experience not only maximizes the visual effect of delivering seasonal and festive theme elements to users, but it also provides a sense of belonging and similarity in the theme park based on difference from daily life. (Jo, 2021) showed a correlation between theme park visitors' satisfaction, loyalty, and intent to revisit and experience marketing with makeup services. The make-up service (Halloween, Zombie, Fairy, Cartoon Character, and so on) interaction at the theme park not only looks to maximize the visual impact of supplying seasonal and festive theme elements to customers, but it also conveys a sense of togetherness and likeness in the theme park attributed to differences from everyday life. To achieve the objective, 668 theme park visitors were interviewed as participants in the study once undergoing a convenience screening. In supporting the findings, the research used analysis procedures such as frequency analysis, reliability verification, factor analysis, and structural equation modeling. There is a favorable impact on customer satisfaction and loyalty when examining the experience marketing using makeup services. The tourist's intention to return is influenced by the beneficial impact on satisfaction and customer loyalty.

Nguyen, H., Nguyen, T., et al. (2021) conducted research on the factors that can affect tourists' return intention in Binh Quoi Village, Vietnam. To identify the factors, the researchers used both quantitative and qualitative research methods. The data needed was gathered through questionnaires and they were able to obtain 207 responses from domestic tourists in Binh Quoi Village. The sample size was identified with the use of a convenience sampling method. Subsequently, the data collected were processed with the use of SPSS 22 software, Cronbach's Alpha Test, Exploratory Factor Analysis, and Multivariate Linear Regression. The findings revealed that Infrastructure, Entertainment services, Reasonable price, Destination image, Local cuisine, Natural environment, and People are the factors that can affect tourists' return intention in Binh Quoi Village.

While several studies were able to identify the physical factors that can affect tourists' return intention, Kim (2021) emphasized the behavioral and psychological factors. It focuses more on tourists' satisfaction and push and pull motivation. The study is an empirical research based on statistical analysis. Data used in the analysis were collected through a random sampling survey with 387 respondents. Furthermore, linear or OLS regression analysis was used to explore the impact of satisfaction and motivation on tourists' return intention in Korea. The findings indicated that the behavioral and psychological factors had a remarkable effect on the revisit intention of tourists. Moreover, the researcher pointed out that although there is a significant relationship between satisfaction, motivation, and revisit intention; push and pull motivation have a more significant effect on revisit intention rather than tourists' satisfaction.

Puspitasari, et al. (2018) conducted a study about the factors that can affect tourists' return intention in Semarang, Indonesia based on the technology acceptance model (TAM) of Ranjbarian & Pool (2015) which focuses in determining the relationship between perceived quality, perceived value, satisfaction, and revisit intention. The research results showed that tourists' satisfaction has the most significant impact when it comes to tourists' return intention in the city of Semarang. Perceived quality has no direct impact on tourist satisfaction nor tourists' return intention. However, perceived quality

affected revisit intention and satisfaction through perceived value of the tourist. This will result in a chain reaction, higher perceived quality will impact the perceived value of the tourist and higher perceived value can enhance tourist satisfaction. Consequently, when tourists are satisfied with their visit in Semarang, it will lead to a higher tourists' return intention rate in the city.

Khuong & Nguyen (2017) hypothesized that there are nine (9) factors affecting the revisit intention of tourists directly and indirectly. The independent factors are Destination Image, Perceived price, Natural Environment, Cultural Attractions, Food, Safety and Security, Negative Attributes, Recreation and Entertainment, Infrastructure. Moreover, satisfaction is the intermediate factor and tourist return intention is the dependent factor. The approach of this study is mainly quantitative and the authors built an experimental design based on the independent factors to test their hypothesis. The results indicated that the independent factors and destination satisfaction of tourists have direct and indirect effects on tourists' return intention. In addition, the results also showed that destination satisfaction is the dominant factor that positively impacts tourists' return intention.

KKGD Reyes et al. (2020) indicated that when determining the drivers of destination attractiveness, the highest driving factor to a visit is adventures and enjoyable events. Activities, infrastructural facilities, and development, unique characteristics, accommodation, leisure & window-shopping centers, natural elements, as well as price & cost are all important aspects of a destination's attraction. In addition, location is an important consideration when touring a destination. It was concluded that cultural influences and infrastructure are essential for a tourist's repeat visits, since all other components, apart from recreational and shopping amenities, are tourist motivating factors.

III. METHODOLOGY

As mentioned by Zhang, Wu, and Buhalis (2017), tourists' experiences have a significant impact in affecting their decision to revisit. The use of qualitative research design is enabling the researchers to analyze tourists' experience, perception and statement through content analysis, which will be used to formulate strategies to improve tourists' return intention in Walt Disney World's Magic Kingdom Theme Park. The purposive sampling approach was chosen throughout the data extraction, with the videos (vlogs from YouTube) coming from first-time to second-time tourists in Walt Disney World's Magic Kingdom Theme Park. The sampling unit/size will be determined by the number of vlogs that can fit in the criteria set by the researchers. The vlog should contain the following criteria: 1) Walt Disney World's Magic Kingdom Theme Park as the setting 2) Narrated their experience or merely the video of Walt Disney World's Magic Kingdom Theme Park 3) Duration of the vlog should be at least two (2) minutes long 4) The vlog should be uploaded in between 2016-2022.

TABLE 1. NUMBER OF VIDEOS

Name of the channel	Title of the vlog/year	Link	Duration of the video	Frequency of vloggers (2 nd , 3 rd visit, etc.)
Janet and Kate	I. We went to Walt Disney World! Part 2! (2019)	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=SSx7Bor4D1g	18:33	2nd
Janet and Kate	II. We went to Walt Disney World! Part 3 WINTER VACATION! (2022)	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Q4uhkPJke_c	26:50	3rd
THE DISNEY TWINS UK	III. MAGIC KINGDOM - DAY ONE - WALT DISNEY WORLD 2022 VLOG (2022)	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=M8Wqt7N58qk	37:34	2nd
Sophie Charlton	IV. OUR FIRST DAY AT MAGIC KINGDOM WALT DISNEY WORLD VLOGS APRIL 2022 ORLANDO VLOGS 2022 (2022)	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=VS6IMcTloow	45:45	2nd
Mummy Of Four Does Disney	V. WALT DISNEY WORLD MAGIC KINGDOM VLOG (2022)	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Q2_KGYtuIas	27:26	2nd
Adventures in Design	VI. How Does Magic Kingdom Feel the Second Time???(2022)	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=CZtl3yOzahE	21:16	2nd

TOM&EL	VII. DAY 1 DISNEY WORLD FLORIDA VLOG! Magic Kingdom, Enchantment Show, Big Thunder Mountain + More! (2022)	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0UOjrdozdn4	29:33	2nd
Hannah Ashton	VIII. WALT DISNEY WORLD VLOG college bestie trip 2022 (2022)	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1ZxvIwlzYfE	25:01	2nd
Flying The Nest	IX. Disney World Orlando - Magic Kingdom Florida Vlog (2019)	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=k7E1-jzMIpg	11:02	2nd
Emily Enchanted	X. WALT DISNEY WORLD 50TH ANNIVERSARY VLOG new cavalcades, characters, disney enchantment, and more! (2021)	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=BC-at_iIKs	19:20	2nd
Adam Hattan	XI. WALT DISNEY WORLD SOLO VLOG DAY 2 SOLO DINING & HARMONIOUS FEBRUARY 2022 ADAM HATTAN (2022)	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=B1X-lnqE1P8	40:44	2nd

Secondary data means accessing large amounts of second-hand information from books, web articles, vlogs, etc. for research purposes. This attempts to address a recent research topic or explore a different aspect on a past study's topic. The data collection method relies on second-hand data coming from vlogs made by various tourists (vloggers) during and after their first or second visit in Walt Disney World's Magic Kingdom Theme Park. Since the study mainly focuses on the content analysis of the various vlogs made by tourists towards their experience in the Walt Disney World's Magic Kingdom Theme Park, the vlogs are then used as a basis because it fits to the criteria created by the researchers. As tourists' experiences are more expressed through personal vlogs and are posted in a streaming site called Youtube that makes it available for use.

After the collection of data, the researchers are going to organize, interpret, analyze the transcribed data and will be presented through series of narration with certain phases in coding the information in categories they belong to among the six return intention factors which are the tourist destination contentment, image of the destination, infrastructure, cost, cultural and natural environment, and safety and security.

In terms of the fair use policy of Youtube, the researchers will only use the vlogs for transformative and educational purposes only. This legal doctrine allows the researchers to use the copyright-protected materials without the permission of the channel owners.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

TABLE 2. TOURISTS' DESTINATION SATISFACTION

Timestamp	Tourists' Destination Satisfaction
I. 1:48	"Every year that we come here, the rides made my stomach drop, it was kind of scary but fun"
I. 5:35	"From the moment you enter the park the experience is fantastic, right from the staff to the theming"
I. 14:17	"The park just opened and the waiting time for the Avatar ride is up to 90-minutes already"
II. 0:08	"We loved our visits at Magic Kingdom, and we're gonna be skipping a couple of days off to school to go on a little winter vacation to Disney"
II. 1:19	"This place is so fun, this park is very suited for children, but does have rides suited for adults too"
II. 9:20	"Now we're going to go to the star wars galaxy edge, it's a new area and we've never been there before and we're gonna go check out the rides"

II. 13:35	“The lines are so crazy, we have to wait for 310-minutes for the ride star wars rise of the resistance”
II. 21:54	“I really enjoy going to Magic Kingdom and we’re going to be doing all the rides again”
II. 26:05	“Come for the rides, but stay for the fireworks. This firework display is the best I have ever seen, it is really a magical place”
II. 26:28	“We had a lot of fun even though there are some rides are closed for refurbishment”
III. 6:55	“We watched the Let the Magic Begin which is the welcome show, it makes me cry, literally like get you crying out the way”
III. 8:44	“The park is crowded and wait time is massive”
III. 21:54	“We just watched the new and improved Friendship Fair, compared to the previous years, it was so good and lovely, I was expecting that they made a couple of changes but they made a few extra changes, new songs and costumes. I wasn’t expecting like a whole new show”
III. 28:35	“So we’ve just watched the Festival of Fantasy Parade that’s been missing for years, my goodness as soon as that music came in like the tears started coming, and yeah we are so happy to have it back”
III. 34:37	“We’ve come to the end of day one, such a magical and fun day at Magic Kingdom. It’s so nice to be back”
IV. 13:02	“It is crazy how busy it is in here, the excruciating long lines is insane”
IV. 16:17	“We’re so happy, we feel like we’re more grateful for this trip because of everything that’s happened in the last two years”
IV. 27:41	“Just being in the park is an experience, but then going on rides and going into shops and seeing Disney characters roaming around just adds to the awe of the place”
IV. 36:28	“We haven’t met the characters because we are not willing to wait for long lines, and I’m not willing to pay for it either because it is too expensive”
IV. 43:18	“Today the fireworks were absolutely incredible, we loved it, it was so good. Ryan said he felt emotion, it was very good, but it was just chaotic, absolute chaos”
V. 2:37	“It’s so lovely to be greeted by Mickey and Minnie in there. Yes! Yes! Yes! This place is so emotional, I can feel myself welling up already.”
V. 14:57	“I don’t know if it’s just because there were wheelchairs getting on and off. Wow either way it was up and running again pretty quickly. There was also a little bit of queue in the lightning lane but not too bad.”
V. 15:33	“The system here in Disney is very good. It’s all done through the app and we found it very helpful for our visit.”
V. 17:57	“It’s another cavalcade and it’s my favorite one. It’s the magic he’s calling the fifth year this one makes me cry, I’m not gonna lie to you.”
VI. 2:56	“I just can’t help but smile and laugh like it is it’s just more of what I love. It’s the thing that I love just upscale bigger and newer. It’s amazing I love it.”
VI. 20:04	“I believe I’ve picked the greatest thing to fall in love with. My heart is full right now. New Disney, new magic people moving fireworks it couldn’t be any better that was an experience.”
VII. 3:06	“Actually, just hear the difference in the staff from Disneyland Paris and Disney World here are just so friendly. The most friendliest people in the world.”
VII. 18:53	“So, if you haven’t already guessed, we are now this is one of my absolute favorites. It’s going to be oh this should be in my top five absolutely it’s not even an amazing ride, but we just love it so much it’s so good.”

VIII. 3:02	“We tried to get the gideons yeah, chocolate chip cookie at the bake house. Fat out it was three hours and like what 50 minutes to wait you had to get in a virtual queue.”
VIII. 13:23	“If you ever come to Disney World, make sure you go to the comedy show because it was so fun it's very interactive.”
IX. 0:01	“Every time you come here; the magic is still there.”
IX. 3:44	“I love how you think every time is just the drop. There is a whole ride to it.”
X. 1:22	“But apparently, it's really crowded, and they also do have the 50th cavalcades.”
X. 4:47	“All of the rides have been very short wait times today”
X. 18:27	“Today was an incredible day. I had so much fun being here on the 50 th , it just meant a lot to me to be able to say that I was here today I was here on the 50 th Anniversary.”
XI. 3:10	“But yeah, I'm happy. I'm good. I'm comfortable. Well, Boma, you get a five out of five”
XI. 14:07	“Wait until at least 2:00, 3:00 PM where most people have come in and gone to World Showcase because the, the line at the moment is crazy busy.”

The results revealed that, of the six factors based on tourist return intention described by Ngoc Khuong et al. (2015), **Table 2** with 37 statements accumulated by the researchers was the most evident factor associated to the return intention of tourists who experienced the Magic Kingdom - Walt Disney. Despite the long lines, guests are pleased with the variety of rides, friendly staff, and excellent entertainment offered by the theme park.

“I really enjoy going to Magic Kingdom and we’re going to be doing all the rides again”

“Just being in the park is an experience, but then going on rides and going into shops and seeing Disney characters roaming around just adds to the awe of the place”

“We just watched the new and improved Friendship Fair, compared to the previous years, it was so good and lovely, I was expecting that they made a couple of changes but they made a few extra changes, new songs and costumes. I wasn’t expecting like a whole new show”

“Every time you come here; the magic is still there.”

“Actually, just hear the difference in the staff from Disneyland Paris and Disney World here are just so friendly. The most friendliest people in the world.”

“The lines are so crazy, we have to wait for 3-10 minutes for the ride star wars rise of the resistance”

“The park is crowded and wait time is massive”

Throughout the guests' exploration of the theme park, there also occurred a comparison between the tourists' first visit to the theme park and their present experience at the theme park. This was prominent in the vlogs that discussed what tourists recalled from their prior visit along with their most unforgettable part of the trip. As stated by Milman and Tasci (2017), if satisfaction and loyalty were influenced by previous trips, the number of previous visits, and staying overnight at the theme park's destination. The analysis presented the influence of number of visits on the probability of returning to theme parks.

TABLE 3. INFRASTRUCTURE

Timestamp	Infrastructure
I. 4:19	“The monorail that we are riding made it so convenient to go to EPCOT”
II. 1:19	“This place is so fun, this park is very suited for children, but does have rides suited for adults too”
II. 7:45	“We’re on the people mover, and we stopped like 15 times already for 30 minutes, it keeps stopping and breaking down”

II. 9:20	“Now we’re going to go to the star wars galaxy edge, it’s a new area and we’ve never been there before and we’re gonna go check out the rides”
II. 26:28	“We had a lot of fun even though there are some rides are closed for refurbishment”
IV. 9:10	“The first time we came together we just never have time to visit the resorts, and it was really on my bucket list to go to Polynesian and eat at Ohana’s and I’m quite nervous because it’s going to make me want to stay at a Disney resort”
IV. 34:48	“Take a moment to appreciate how beautiful fantasyland is in the back of the castle, it’s so stunning”
IV. 39:03	“Hey over there we can see the construction for Tron, I’m so excited for that when we come back”
V. 7:00	“We’ll do mobile checkout and then just scan a qr code. Once you’ve done, it you’ll check out your phone you paid on your phone and then you can leave.”
VI. 3:48	“That is a work of art man. That is a work of art.
VI. 13:02	“Once again there was a big top circus at one point inside of Disneyland. So, this just gives me that vibe of like what that must have been like when there was an actual circus that was inside of Disneyland.”
VII. 3:44	“Oh, the design on that castle is beautiful man! Wait till we get there but that's the first time we've seen it since like you said since it's had the big renovation.”
VII. 11:35	“Actually, as well a lot of the rides have them water stations the water fountain things in the queue so like if you just need a quick drink or something.”
VIII. 4:30	“We made it into our room got checked in it's so cute and nice. Honestly, I've never stayed here but 10 out of 10.”
VIII. 9:40	“How like the technology that they have to it feels like you're on the dragon yeah.”
IX. 4:43	“It's kind of cool that whole dragon is made out of Lego.”
IX. 9:06	“There are parts of the park we just walk straight past or never go on. Didn't know they had a little mermaid ride so we're just gonna go and jump on all the different lines”
X. 2:45	“All of the shops that are kind of behind me over here, everything has gone to a virtual queue, but all the virtual cues are now temporarily unavailable.”
X. 4:15	“Actually, there is a glitch in the system. I guess it's the day of the 50 th . There are going to be glitches, so I think we actually weren't on the list for some reason.”
XI. 2:43	“Buffets are your friend. I feel so much more comfortable in here than I did at the hotel restaurant.”
XI. 4:38	“They've also redesigned the entrance by the looks of things. Put new pathways in, new signage. Ooh! Look at that! In the new font with the 50th Anniversary in the background.”
XI. 6:40	“So behind me, you can see where the old, temporary Mouse Gear was. That's being transformed into the Connections Cafe, which is gonna replace Electric Umbrella, which was originally there.”
XI. 11:55	“I don't like, I still don't like the look of them. I'm just, I'm letting them exist now, because I do like Harmonious.”
XI. 13:49	“Oh, the lagoon's been drained! Oh, I suppose they're working on it.”
XI. 15:43	“Here at the wheelchair and ECV rental, they've got the brand-new Mickey and Minnie push chairs.”
XI. 24:01	“I'm just gonna slip this in very quickly. I noticed on the app there were a few glitches. So, for example, it was still showing our Yacht Club reservation from December. And also, I couldn't cancel Genie plus reservations. Just some like minor glitches.”

Table 3 was followed by Tourist Destination Satisfaction with 26 statements analyzed, which consistently mentioned as something that visitors notice when touring the theme park. The Walt Disney World Resort is a theme park known for its numerous attractions, with over 50 rides, shows, and attractions. It was seen in the vlogs that it can accommodate all visitors.

“The first time we came together we just never have time to visit the resorts, and it was really on my bucket list to go to Polynesian and eat at Ohana’s and I’m quite nervous because it’s going to make me want to stay at a Disney resort”

“Take a moment to appreciate how beautiful fantasyland is in the back of the castle, it’s so stunning”

“This place is so fun, this park is very suited for children, but does have rides suited for adults too”

“Actually, as well a lot of the rides have them water stations the water fountain things in the queue so like if you just need a quick drink or something.”

“Hey over there we can see the construction for Tron, I’m so excited for that when we come back”

“All of the shops that are kind of behind me over here, everything has gone to a virtual queue, but all the virtual cues are now temporarily unavailable.”

“Here at the wheelchair and ECV rental, they’ve got the brand-new Mickey and Minnie push chairs.”

Based from the vlogs, the theme park incorporates, as pointed out by customers, the use of technology such as the lightning lane, applications when booking an attraction, restaurants, and merchandise store. This improved their travel experience and made experience more memorable. According to Jovanovi et al. (2016), infrastructure is any physical component that is built or created for the benefit of tourists. Infrastructures, pertaining to the researchers, included supporting amenities, equipment, and workforce that are necessary for the operation of every tourism destination. With the improvement of the theme park’s infrastructure, this is essential for repeat visits, because all other components, aside from recreational and shopping amenities, are tourist motivating factors to return (KKGD Reyes et al. 2020).

TABLE 4. DESTINATION IMAGE

Timestamp	Destination Image
I. 18:08	“What can I say out of the whole Disney Parks experience, Magic Kingdom is the best most magical place”
II. 26:05	“Come for the rides, but stay for the fireworks. This firework display is the best I have ever seen, it is really a magical place”
III. 0:15	“We are here at the most magical place on earth, Magic Kingdom, we usually come at this time of the year, it’s a tradition”
III. 34:37	“We’ve come to the end of day one, such a magical and fun day at Magic Kingdom. It’s so nice to be back”
IV. 3:10	“Here we are Magic Kingdom, where dreams come true”
IV. 27:41	“Just being in the park is an experience, but then going on rides and going into shops and seeing Disney characters roaming around just adds to the awe of the place”
VI. 1:24	“It’s so big and fancy. Fancy that’s the way to say it. Disneyland is so humble, but this is big and fancy.”
VIII. 1:08	“We’re so excited, you guys are gonna see the best of it the food the drinks the rides the parade.”
VIII. 3:53	“I just thought it was so vintage it reminds me of like a nostalgic 2000s Disney”
IX. 0:0	“Every time you come here; the magic is still there.”
IX. 0:51	“So excited that we are finally back because this is the big one Disney World is the ultimate of ultimate Disney parks to come to.”
IX. 2:14	“So today we’re doing magic kingdom and honestly, we’ve done it a few times, but I swear every time you come here the magic is still there. ”
X. 16:58	“Honestly, really really liked watching it from the main street. I felt like it was a bit more magical because you actually see everything.”
XI. 5:53	“My expectation or my hope rather, is that because Test Track is part of early entry, and most people are like with family staying in Disney resorts. Single rider should just be like straight on.”

Comprised of 14 statements gathered from the vlogs presented in relation to **Table 4**. The Magic Kingdom has consistently been thought of as the most magical place on earth. Theme represents a big part of what makes Disney World so magical. This transports visitors to a completely different world.

“Just being in the park is an experience, but then going on rides and going into shops and seeing Disney characters roaming around just adds to the awe of the place”

“So today we're doing Magic Kingdom and honestly, we've done it a few times, but I swear every time you come here the magic is still there. ”

“What can I say out of the whole Disney Parks experience, Magic Kingdom is the best most magical place”

“Come for the rides, but stay for the fireworks. This firework display is the best I have ever seen, it is really a magical place”

“It's so big and fancy. Fancy that's the way to say it. Disneyland is so humble, but this is big and fancy.”

“I just thought it was so vintage it reminds me of like a nostalgic 2000s Disney”

“Every time you come here; the magic is still there.”

Magic Kingdom Park is the most popular attraction, with an extraordinary castle that is even more magical at night through to its fireworks display. Most travelers' vlogs highlighted the castle and fireworks at night, which had a significant impact on their visit because it was recognized as one of the most memorable experience an individual can have. The destination image has a considerable influence on tourists' tendency to return (Zhang et al., 2017). Jebbouri et al. (2022) described destination image as "the collection of beliefs, ideas, and impressions that a tourist has to a destination or attraction that was prominent on how the tourists were drawn to the theme park and the feature that makes it special."

TABLE 5. PRICE

Timestamp	Price
III. 11:53	“We’ve got a lightning lane for Under the Sea, it’s a bit pricey, but I hope we’re gonna get something out of it”
IV. 3:49	“We are paying a bloody fortune for this Magic Kingdom experience, and we just saved 25 dollars for parking”
IV. 36:28	“We haven’t met the characters because we are not willing to wait for long lines, and I’m not willing to pay for it either because it is too expensive”
V. 16:17	“So, we've got two-foot-long hot dogs between the sectors which is apple two portions of fries one of which are chili fries and a bunch cake just to um keep us going.”
VII. 1:12	“If you don't know and you're staying on site at a Disney World hotel, you get all your transport transportation to and from the parks completely free yeah which is amazing.”
VII. 1:21	“In the past, we've actually hired a car, but they put the prices up now. So now if you get a car, you've got to pay for it in the theme park car parks you've got to pay for it yeah, the hotel car pack it just gets a little bit cost costly.”
VII. 6:31	“Basically, we have purchase genie plus today which I think came to about thirty dollars which is pretty pricey full we're just going to do it for each part one exactly.”
VIII. 7:17	“We're gonna like just to split and snack all day that's what we decided so, we can eat more food so we can just eat more and try new more things right.”
IX. 1:22	“If you wanted to grab your tickets, I'll leave a link below there's a little promo code if you wanted to save some money on your Disney tickets.”
XI. 16:54	“So, let's see what else I can get. I just managed to book a return time for Soarin' at 2:50! Should work out quite nicely.”
XI. 20:14	“I'll give that a solid four outta five, really nice. It was affordable for what I thought I got.”
XI. 30:35	“Just researching DVC. - Oh nice! - You got me into being a DVC member! - I make people spend a lot of money.”

Table 5 shows that even though Magic Kingdom is too costly, tourists are willing to pay for the experience. As stated in the study of Ngoc Khuong et al. (2015), tourists are eager to spend more if they recognize the company with luxurious brands.

“We’ve got a lightning lane for Under the Sea, it’s a bit pricey, but I hope we’re gonna get something out of it”

“We are paying a bloody fortune for this Magic Kingdom experience, and we just saved 25 dollars for parking”

“We haven’t met the characters because we are not willing to wait for long lines, and I’m not willing to pay for it either because it is too expensive”

“In the past, we’ve actually hired a car, but they put the prices up now. So now if you get a car, you’ve got to pay for it in the theme park car parks you’ve got to pay for it yeah, the hotel car park it just gets a little bit cost costly.”

“Basically, we have purchase genie plus today which I think came to about thirty dollars which is pretty pricey full we’re just going to do it for each part one exactly.”

“If you wanted to grab your tickets, I’ll leave a link below there’s a little promo code if you wanted to save some money on your Disney tickets.”

Magic Kingdom is a place where tourists can escape into fantasy. The price that comes with it was really pointed out by most tourists in the videos. However, comparing Magic Kingdom prices to other theme park offerings is a challenge, as there’s simply “nothing else like it.” And various travelers, are still willing to pay for such an experience.

TABLE 6. NATURAL AND CULTURAL

Timestamp	Natural and Cultural
I. 1:59	“Every time that we come to the water park it is raining, there is no shade and seating”
VI. 5:12	“Look at all these green and garden spaces. This is part of what I found to be so charming was just that extra space.”
VI. 6:28	“Probably my biggest surprise about loving magic kingdom is there’s just so much history of Disneyland. It’s still very much alive here and that is something that I really really appreciate and cherish.”
XI. 25:07	“If you’re British, I had no idea what was going on. No idea. Really. There were some things I picked up on and, and like, I knew of American history wise.”

Table 6 accumulated the least statements that tourists give notice to at the theme park. The focus of the tourists is mostly on the attractions and the overall experience of the trip. Although one tourist mentioned about not having shade during a hot weather. According to Tifferet and Vilnai-Yavetz (2017), nature elements in a commercial environment can affect emotional responses of satisfaction or, to a small extent, customer behavior. Even with the modern tourist’s demands and new trends, this factor still influences that improves the viability and competitiveness of places, districts, and states.

“Every time that we come to the water park it is raining, there is no shade and seating”

“Look at all these green and garden spaces. This is part of what I found to be so charming was just that extra space.”

“Probably my biggest surprise about loving magic kingdom is there’s just so much history of Disneyland. It’s still very much alive here and that is something that I really really appreciate and cherish.”

“If you’re British, I had no idea what was going on. No idea. Really. There were some things I picked up on and, and like, I knew of American history wise.”

TABLE 7. SAFETY AND SECURITY

Timestamp	Safety and Security
I. 1:59	“Every time that we come to the water park it is raining, there is no shade and seating”
II. 7:45	“We’re on the people mover, and we stopped like 15 times already for 30 minutes, it keeps stopping and breaking down”
IV. 41:18	“Too many people and not enough security. The lines for the fireworks did not matter, they disappeared and so did the walkway. It was quite chaotic!”

IV. 43:18	“Today the fireworks were absolutely incredible, we loved it, it was so good. Ryan said he felt emotion, it was very good, but it was just chaotic, absolute chaos”
V. 1:33	“Anyways, we now need to go through bag check which incidentally my bag buzzes at least someone's bag buzzes every single time bar one only once have we gone through bag check.”
X. 12:01	“Wish me luck, about to go to the security.”
XI. 3:03	“The only downside is having to either take your bag with you or like trusting the people next to you to look after it for you.”
XI. 4:06	“[Bus Announcement] We're on our way to Epcot. For your safety and the safety of others, please remain seated while the vehicle is in motion”
XI. 6:58	“[Ride Announcer] Hello. The seatbelt check is around the corner. For your safety, remain seated with your seatbelt fastened, and your hands, arms, and legs inside the vehicle at all times.”
XI. 23:09	“I quite like the social distanced character meet and greets. I know it's not the same as like actually meeting them, hugging them, talking to them, that kind of stuff. But yeah, it's just nice atmosphere, I think.”

Table 7 presents the problems when it comes to Safety and Security within the theme park. Mostly the concern that was highlighted in the videos, the park is too overcrowded. Lines are too long for the rides, and there are few to no umbrellas or shaded areas available in the park, tourists are forced to stand while waiting in the heat of the sun or get wet from the rain. Here are some examples:

“Every time that we come to the water park it is raining, there is no shade and seating”

“We’re on the people mover, and we stopped like 15 times already for 30 minutes, it keeps stopping and breaking down”

“Too many people and not enough security. The lines for the fireworks did not matter, they disappeared and so did the walkway. It was quite chaotic!”

“Today the fireworks were absolutely incredible, we loved it, it was so good. Ryan said he felt emotion, it was very good, but it was just chaotic, absolute chaos”

“The only downside is having to either take your bag with you or like trusting the people next to you to look after it for you.”

Although Magic Kingdom is known to be the most magical place on earth, all the videos suggest that Magic Kingdom should also make a more comprehensive approach to safety and security of their theme park visitors.

V. CONCLUSION

The research made use of a qualitative research design adapted from the study based on the tourist return intention of Ngoc Khuong et al. (2015), that enables the researchers to analyze visitors' experiences, perceptions, and statements using content analysis. This information will be adopted to generate means to enhance tourists' return intention in Walt Disney World's Magic Kingdom Theme Park. Purposive sampling was implemented throughout the data extraction process, with the videos (YouTube vlogs) ranging from second-time or more visits to Walt Disney World's Magic Kingdom Theme Park. The number of vlogs that follow the researchers' criteria will determine the sampling unit/size.

By transcribing the eleven videos, data shows that the five factors, namely, destination image, tourists’ satisfaction, infrastructure, natural and cultural, and safety and security showed significance in terms of their impact on guests' intent to return to a theme park. The data indicates that the concept of Tourists’ Destination Satisfaction emerged as the most prominent factor on return intention of tourists in the theme park. Followed by, Infrastructure, Destination image, Safety and Security, and Price. On the other hand, the Natural and Cultural factor was rarely mentioned in all the videos gathered, which suggests that it is not a major consideration when it comes to determining whether tourists intend to return to a theme park.

Based on the findings, Magic Kingdom Theme Park - Walt Disney World ought to emphasize on elevating the destination image to highlight distinctive qualities, while also investing in technology to improve tourists' convenience, comfort, and enjoyment. Improving infrastructure to provide delightful experiences while ensuring safety and security that allow visitors to feel comfortable. Incorporating cultural features such as local art, music, and cuisine into the park creates a unique and

authentic experience. Ultimately, prioritize visitor satisfaction with the purpose of exceeding the needs of guests whilst considering feedback into account. Theme parks that adopt such approaches can provide visitors with a memorable and wonderful experience, increasing tourist return intention and recommending the park to others.

REFERENCES

- [1] Chen, H. & Rahman, I. (2018). Cultural tourism; An analysis of engagement, cultural, contact, memorable tourism experience and destination loyalty. *Tourism Management Perspectives*, 26, 153-163
- [2] Cheng, Z.; Chen, X. The Effect of Tourism Experience on Tourists' Environmentally Responsible Behavior at Cultural Heritage Sites: The Mediating Role of Cultural Attachment. *Sustainability* (2022), 14, 565. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su1401056>
- [3] Delos Reyes, K., Fondevilla, C., Hernandez, P., Silang, M., Penana, M., & Felicen, S. (2020). *DETERMINING DRIVERS OF DESTINATION ATTRACTIVENESS IN BATANGAS PROVINCE, PHILIPPINES*.
- [4] Godovykh, M., Milman, A., Tasci, A., Godovykh, M., & Tasci, A. (2019). Original Citation Original Citation. <https://stars.library.ucf.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1954&context=ucfscholar>
- [5] Jebbouri, A., Zhang, H., Imran, Z., Iqbal, J., & Bouchiba, N. (2022). Impact of Destination Image Formation on Tourist Trust: Mediating Role of Tourist Satisfaction. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.845538>
- [6] Jebrane, E. M., & Ouariti, O. Z. (2020). The impact of transport infrastructure on tourism destination attractiveness: A case study of Marrakesh City, Morocco. *African Journal of Hospitality, Tourism and Leisure*, 9(2). https://www.ajhtl.com/uploads/7/1/6/3/7163688/article_36_vol_9_2__2020_morocco.pdf
- [7] Jo, Y., & Rhee, Y.-J. (2021). The relationship between experiential marketing using makeup services and theme park participants' satisfaction, loyalty and intention to return. *The Research Journal of the Costume Culture*, 29(5), 706–718. <https://doi.org/10.29049/rjcc.2021.29.5.706>
- [8] Kuong, M. N., & Nguyen, T. T. (2015, January). Factors affecting tourists' return intention towards Vung Tau City ... Factors Affecting Tourists' Return Intention towards Vung Tau City, Vietnam-A Mediation Analysis of Destination Satisfaction. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/283190627_Factors_Affecting_Tourists'_Return_Intention_towards_Vung_Tau_City_Vietnam-A_Mediation_Analysis_of_Destination_Satisfaction
- [9] Kim, W. (2021). Determinants of Tourists' Revisit Intention in Domestic Tourism. *International Journal of Advanced Culture Technology* Vol.9 No.3 74-80. <https://doi.org/10.17703/IJACT.2021.9.3.74>
- [10] Lee, S., Jeong, E., & Qu, K. (2019). Exploring Theme Park Visitors' Experience on Satisfaction and Revisit Intention: A Utilization of Experience Economy Model. *Journal of Quality Assurance in Hospitality & Tourism*, 21(4), 1–24. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1528008x.2019.1691702>
- [11] Levy, C. (2023, March 2). 14 Reasons Why Is Disney World Really So Magical. *TheTravel*. <https://www.thetravel.com/why-disney-is-so-magical-worth-it/#visitors-get-to-interact-with-disney-characters>
- [12] Mai Ngoc Khuong and Pham Anh Nguyen. (2017) Factors Affecting Tourist Destination Satisfaction and Return Intention – A Study in Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam. *Journal of Economics, Business and Management* Vol. 5, No. 2, pp. 95-102.
- [13] Mai, K. N., Nguyen, P. N. D., & Nguyen, P. T. M. (2019). International tourists' loyalty to Ho Chi Minh City destination—a mediation analysis of perceived service quality and perceived value. *Sustainability*, 11(19), 5447. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11195447>
- [14] Mcleod, S. (2019). Two Years to Remember: The Impact of the Pandemic on Florida's Tourism Industry. *The Impact of the Pandemic on Florida's Tourism Industry*. <https://economics.td.com/us-years-to-remember>
- [15] Nguyen Viet, B., Dang, H. P., & Nguyen, H. H. (2020). Revisit intention and satisfaction: The role of destination image, perceived risk, and cultural contact. *Cogent Business & Management*, 7(1), 1796249. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2020.1796249>

- [16] Niu, Y., Hyejin Park, & Andrei Kirilenko. (2019). Theme Park Visitor Experience and Satisfaction: A Case of TripAdvisor Reviews of Three Theme Parks in Orlando. ScholarWorks@UMass Amherst. https://scholarworks.umass.edu/ttra/2019/research_papers/11/
- [17] Ortegón-Cortázar, L., & Royo-Vela, M. (2019). Nature in malls: Effects of a natural environment on the cognitive image, emotional response, and behaviors of visitors. *European Research on Management and Business Economics*, 25(1), 38–47. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iedeen.2018.08.001>
- [18] Puspitasari, N., Pramono, S., Rahmadhika, A. (2018). AIP Conference Proceedings 2019, 040017; <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.5061887>
- [19] Ryani, L. S., & Soesanto, H. (2021). Factors affecting revisit intention through customer satisfaction in theme park. *International Journal of Economics, Business and Accounting Research (IJEBAR)*, 5(2). <https://doi.org/10.29040/ijebar.v5i2.2294>
- [20] Tate, C., & Kennerly, B. (2020, July 12). Opening day at Disney World: Small crowds, short lines, social distancing and COVID-19 merch. USA TODAY. <https://www.usatoday.com/story/travel/experience/america/theme-parks/2020/07/11/walt-disney-world-reopens-after-4-month-covid-19-shutdown/5412790002/>
- [21] Tifferet, S., & Vilnai-Yavetz, I. (2017). Phytophilia and service atmospherics: The effect of indoor plants on consumers. *Environment and Behavior*, 49(7), 814–844. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/0013916516669390>
- [22] Zhang, H., Wu, Y., & Buhalis, D. (2017). A model of perceived image, memorable tourism experiences and revisit intention. *Journal of Destination Marketing & Management*.